

Environmental Awareness of Students in a Primary School with Zero Waste Policy

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Abstract

In the research conducted to determine the environmental awareness of students in a primary school implementing zero waste policy and to examine zero waste and environmentally friendly practices, an environmental awareness questionnaire and interview technique were used. In the research, a mixed method was used by adopting a quantitative-qualitative sequential transformational design. The quantitative part of the research was carried out with 110 students receiving education within the scope of "Zero Waste Project". The data were interpreted using frequency and arithmetic averages and the environmental awareness of the students was analyzed. The qualitative data of the research were obtained by content analysis of interviews with six teachers. In the light of the research findings, it was determined that the environmental awareness of the students was high. The findings show that students are sensitive about air, water, soil and ecological balance and that zero waste policies positively affect this awareness. The results show that zero waste practices increase students' environmental awareness. Especially on issues such as air, water, soil pollution and ecological balance, students' sensitivity has increased and they have developed environmental awareness.

Keywords: Zero waste, environmental education, environmental awareness, sustainability, primary school student.

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Introduction

We are a product of both nature and nurture. Our sensitivity to climate change, the environment, sustainable world and waste management expresses our nurture. Our nurture influences our nature. Zero waste practices are a measure against situations that negatively affect our environment, nature and nurture. Zero waste policy is an approach that aims to minimize waste starting from the production stage and to maximize the use of waste through methods such as recycling, reuse and energy recovery. Zero waste aims to transform the waste management processes of society and businesses in order to reduce the amount of waste and protect natural resources. This approach supports the principles of environmental protection and sustainability

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by reducing the potential of waste to harm nature. Zero waste reduces the consumption of natural resources and minimizes the impact of waste on the environment by reducing waste generation and bringing waste into the economy through recycling, reuse and recovery. Zero Waste policy provides various economic, environmental and social benefits. It encourages more effective and efficient use of natural resources. Reducing the amount of waste saves energy and water, reduces the consumption of natural resources and reduces the carbon footprint. Recycling and reuse reduce the demand for raw materials, lower energy costs and reduce the risk of environmental pollution (Evans, 2021; Gül & Yaman, 2021; Saleh, 2020; Zaman, 2022).

Since zero waste policy requires effective planning of waste management processes, strengthening waste sorting and recycling infrastructure and raising awareness of the society, it can be assumed that it will increase environmental awareness, change waste management habits and contribute to the adoption of a sustainable lifestyle. Zero waste policy can be seen to be in line with national and international policies that focus on environmental awareness such as resource conservation, waste minimization and recycling. In the 21st century, when environmental problems are increasing and natural resources are being depleted, zero waste policy can be seen as an important step supporting environmental sustainability (Altınok, 2021; Ulusal, 2022; Yüzüak et al., 2022). It can be assumed that individuals who know and implement zero waste policy are more sensitive to the solution of environmental problems and environmental sustainability.

It is clear that there is a strong relationship between zero waste policy and environmental awareness. Zero waste policy aims to reduce the amount of waste, encourage recycling and protect natural resources based on environmental awareness, while environmental awareness is based on principles such as sustainable use of natural resources, reduction of environmental pollution and protection of natural ecosystems. Zero waste policy aims to minimize waste generation, recycle waste into the economy and reduce negative environmental impacts based on the principles of environmental awareness. Zero waste policy encourages more effective and efficient use of resources by transforming waste management processes. Reducing the amount of waste reduces the consumption of natural resources and reduces pressure on the environment. Recycling and reuse, on the other hand, allows waste to be recycled into the economy, can reduce demand for raw materials and increase energy savings. Thus, it can reduce environmental pollution and contribute to the protection of natural ecosystems. The main objective of zero waste policy is to reduce environmental impacts and conserve natural resources by minimizing waste. This policy encourages society and businesses to be more sensitive about waste generation. By adopting practices such as waste reduction, segregation, recycling and reuse, individuals and organizations increase environmental awareness and support a sustainable lifestyle. As a result, zero waste policy is closely related to environmental awareness (Lang, 2005; Ulusal, 2022; Önal et al., 2019; Yüzüak et al., 2022). It can be assumed that zero waste policy supports environmental sustainability by applying the principles of environmental awareness such as reducing waste, promoting recycling and protecting natural resources. Thus, it can be considered that zero waste policy has a positive effect on environmental awareness.

Many studies have emphasized environmental awareness and environmental education to overcome the environmental challenges facing humanity in the 21st century and for a sustainable future (Çabuk & Karacaoğlu, 2003; Değirmenci et al., 2023; Erdem et al.,

2019; Gıcıır et al., 2020; Kurt Konakođlu, 2020; Okada et al., 2019; Sođukpınar & Karıřan Korucu, 2020; Yeřil & Turan, 2020; Yeřilyurt et al. 2020). In these studies, the contribution of environmental awareness to the existence and future of the world is undoubtedly very valuable. In particular, the environmental awareness questionnaire developed by abuk and Karacaođlu (2003) has been used in many studies and has brought an important contribution to environmental education and awareness studies in Turkey by receiving nearly five hundred citations.

In today's world where the amount of consumption increases rapidly, zero waste policy, which gains importance as recycling, recovery and reuse, should be seen as a part of environmental awareness. Despite the studies revealing that various variables have an effect on attitudes towards zero waste and recycling, which concern all areas of life (Karatekin et al., 2023), there is a need to go beyond hypothetical opinions about how effective zero waste practices are on the environmental awareness of primary school students. Moreover, considering the results of the research (Atınok, 2021; abuk & Karacaođlu, 2003), which emphasize that curricula and textbooks are insufficient in terms of content on environmental education and zero waste, the environmental awareness of students in a school that adopts and implements a zero waste project or policy has been a matter of curiosity.

Investigating the environmental awareness of primary school students is important in terms of adopting sustainability principles to children, developing environmental consciousness and protection behaviors and creating a society that can produce solutions to environmental problems for future generations. Primary school period is a period in which children's basic values, knowledge and behaviors are formed. When environmental awareness and sustainability concepts are introduced to children at this age, these values and consciousness are further developed and strengthened in the following years. Instilling environmental consciousness in primary school students enables them to adopt sustainability principles such as protecting natural resources, waste reduction and recycling. Especially waste reduction and recycling are important for environmental sustainability (Alaydin et al., 2014; Chawla, 1999; Gökdere, 2005; Jinliang et al., 2004). In this way, a more environmentally sensitive and responsible society can be created in the future. Primary school students are in a period when they start to form their consumption habits. Trainings on environmental awareness and zero waste will provide them with correct and conscious consumption habits. Steps such as preferring sustainable products and reducing the use of plastic will enable children to adopt an environmentally friendly lifestyle in the future. Investigating the environmental sensitivity of primary school students will contribute to the development of their environmental awareness and protection behaviors and will provide children with environmentally friendly behaviors such as recycling habits, energy and water saving and will provide clues that these behaviors will become a part of their future lives. Social awareness on environmental issues can be created by raising awareness about environmental sensitivity and sharing it with their families and their environment. Active participation of children in environmental projects and activities will help to increase environmental awareness in the society and to take action for sustainability.

In the studies conducted by Alaydin et al. (2014); Chawla (1999), Gökdere (2005), Jinliang et al. (2004), the environmental awareness of primary school students and the importance of primary school period in terms of environmental awareness were emphasized. Because of this importance, the environmental awareness of primary school students should be considered worthy of research. In this research, it was seen

as a problem how the environmental sensitivity of the students who received training on zero waste through a series of seminars and practices in their schools and in which dimensions they are more sensitive to the environment. In the light of this problem, the aim of the research is to determine the environmental awareness of students in a primary school implementing zero waste policy and to examine zero waste and environmentally friendly practices. In line with this purpose, answers to the following questions will be sought.

1. What is the level of environmental sensitivity of the students?
2. What are the environmental sensitivities of the students regarding air pollution, water pollution, soil pollution, ecological balance, participation in environmental studies?
3. What are the students' views on environmental education?
4. What is the effect of zero waste policy on environmental awareness?
5. What are successful zero waste and environmentally friendly practices according to teachers' views?
6. According to teachers' views, what is the effect of waste and environmental protection education on student behaviors?
7. According to teachers' views, how do students' environmental awareness change after the implementation of zero waste policies?
8. According to teachers' views, what can be done about zero waste and environmentally friendly practices?

Materials and Methods

In the research, mixed method was adopted in which quantitative and qualitative research methods were used together. The research is descriptive because it reveals the current situation and it is aimed to collect in-depth information in the research.

Participants

Quantitative research was conducted with 110 students who received training through seminars within the scope of the "Zero Waste Project" at Yeni Turan Primary School in Turkey. In the school where the research was conducted, within the scope of the Zero Waste Project, regular and inclusive applied seminars and trainings have been carried out for five years in order to create nature awareness in students, to support the recycling of waste, to ensure change and development in children with the relationship between healthy life and environmental pollution. Within the scope of these activities, information seminars on planting saplings and putting waste materials in waste bins are held with students. In addition, nature trips and information on nature cleaning, atmosphere and air pollution are regularly organized. In the school garden, vegetables planted by students are grown, birdhouses and tubular cat feeders made from waste materials are prepared, and feeders are made from waste materials. Qualitative research was conducted with six teachers in this school, which carries out zero waste practices, using a semi-structured interview form.

Data Collection

In the study, "Environmental Awareness Questionnaire", which was previously developed by Çabuk & Karacaoğlu (2003) in an application with university students,

was used to collect quantitative data. In the application with university students, the alpha reliability coefficient (α) of the questionnaire was found to be 0.81. Factor analysis test was used for the construct validity of the sub-factors, and as a result of the factor analysis, it was determined by the owners of the questionnaire that all of the 24 items determined for the trial form were appropriate. In this study, factor analysis was performed to check the applicability of the questionnaire to primary school students. Bartlett's test value, which was performed to determine whether the data matrix was a unit matrix and whether the correlation between the variables was sufficient, was above 0.60. If the P value is <0.05 , the data set is suitable for factor analysis. In the pre-test application with primary school students, Cronbach's alpha coefficient was determined as 0,817 to explain or question the internal consistency of the items and the homogeneous structure of the items in the questionnaire. According to this result, it can be said that the items in the questionnaire are consistent with each other and consist of items that measure the same feature.

A semi-structured interview form was used to collect qualitative data. The following questions were included in the interview form:

1. What are the zero waste and environmentally friendly practices that you find successful in your school?
2. Have you observed that waste and environmental protection trainings have made a change in your students?
3. How was the environmental awareness of the students after the implementation of zero waste policies in your school?
4. What else would you suggest to be done about zero waste and environmentally friendly practices in your school?

Since qualitative and quantitative data collection tools were used together in the study, mixed method was adopted. In the same study, mixed research method was used because it involves the collection, analysis and interpretation of both qualitative and quantitative research data.

Typologies of mixed methods research designs are mostly developed based on the approaches used in evaluation. According to Pardede (2019), cited by Creswell (2012), in the context of educational research, mixed methods research designs are categorized into six main types: Three sequential (explanatory, exploratory and transformative) and three convergent or parallel (triangulation, nested and transformative). In the study, quantitative data were collected and analyzed first and then qualitative data were collected. For this reason, a quantitative-qualitative sequential transformational design was adopted in the study. Sequential transformational design; quantitative (QUAL - qualitative) data can be collected and analyzed first and then qualitative data can be obtained or, conversely, qualitative (QUAL - quantitative) data can be collected and analyzed first and then quantitative data can be obtained (Butgel et al., 2016).

Data Analysis

The quantitative data obtained with the environmental awareness questionnaire were analyzed in computer environment using SPSS (Statistical Packet for Social Sciences) program. In order to examine the environmental awareness of the students, the data were interpreted by using frequency and arithmetic averages. The arithmetic mean of the obtained data was interpreted as no environmental awareness between 0 and 0,66, partial awareness between 0,66 and 1,33, and high awareness between 1,33 and 2,00.

In the study, the data collected through interviews with six teachers were interpreted using a qualitative approach with content analysis method. Content analysis can be used mostly in qualitative research and may include different coding and categorization techniques to answer research questions or to support theoretical frameworks. While applying the content analysis method with coding and categorization processes by following the basic steps in the research, firstly, themes were identified to examine and understand the data. These themes were created based on the research questions and provided a framework for making sense of the content of the interview data. Then, each interview was carefully analyzed and key words or phrases containing the themes were identified. Thus, the coding process was initiated. The interview data were coded around these key words and phrases. These codes represented the content of each interview. After the coding was completed, the frequencies of each code were calculated. This helped to understand how often each code occurred and which themes were most emphasized. Frequency analysis allowed the data to be summarized and the main findings to be extracted. The frequency analyses were then tabulated and used in the research as a visual representation of your data. These tables were used to answer the research questions and understand the data. The tables helped to better understand and interpret the results of the research.

Results

In accordance with the quantitative-qualitative sequential transformational design adopted in the study, quantitative data were first collected and analyzed and then qualitative data were interpreted.

The findings were obtained by analyzing the data obtained from 110 students in the sample of the study. The findings were interpreted by using frequency and arithmetic averages. The findings obtained by unpaired t-test were interpreted to see whether the students' graduation status of the faculty of education and their beliefs about the adequacy of environmental education in schools make a difference in their environmental sensitivity. The findings obtained by ANOVA on whether there is a significant difference between the seniority of the students and their environmental sensitivity are also interpreted.

Table 1. Environmental Awareness of Students about Air Pollution

Questions	Always	Sometimes	Never	\bar{x}
	f	f	f	
1. Are you careful not to use consumer goods (deodorants and other sprays) that contain substances harmful to the ozone layer?	98	12	0	1,89
2. Even if you have your own car, do you use public transport, taking care not to cause air pollution?	61	48	1	1,55
3. Do you make sure that other people are not affected when you talk and use various tools?	103	7	0	1,94
4. Do you warn people to be sensitive about air pollution?	96	14	0	1,87
Total	N=110		7,25/4	1,81

As seen in Table 1, the arithmetic mean of the answers given to the questions about air pollution was found to be 1.81. It can be said that students in a primary school implementing zero waste policy have high environmental awareness about air pollution. The highest arithmetic mean (1.89) related to air pollution was the mean of the answers given to the question "Do you pay attention not to affect other people while talking and using various tools?". It can be said that most of the students always pay attention to the fact that other people are not affected while talking and using various tools. According to the answers given by the students, the lowest arithmetic mean (1,55) was the mean of the answers given to the question "Even if you have your own car, do you use public transport taking into account not to cause air pollution?". 1 out of 110 students stated that even if they had their own car, they would never use public transport taking into account not causing air pollution. On the other hand, 48 of the students stated that they sometimes use public transport in order not to cause air pollution. According to these data, it can be said that a significant portion of the students will not always prefer public transport. It can be said that students are less sensitive about using public transport in order not to cause air pollution. It can be said that students are less sensitive about using public transport by taking into account not causing air pollution. The findings related to the environmental sensitivity of students regarding air pollution show that students in primary schools implementing zero waste policy are generally sensitive about air pollution, especially more sensitive about not affecting other people. However, it was found that they were relatively less sensitive about using public transport even if they had their own vehicles and sometimes did not consider not causing air pollution when making choices in this regard.

Table 2. Environmental Awareness of Students about Water Pollution

Questions	Always	Sometimes	Never	\bar{x}
	f	f	f	
5. Do you buy cleaning products carefully to check whether they contain harmful chemicals?	75	35	0	1,68
6. Do you use water sparingly under all circumstances?	98	12	0	1,89
7. Do you take care to prevent harmful chemicals such as motor oil and paint from entering the sewerage system?	88	22	0	1,80
8. Do you warn people to be sensitive about water pollution?	100	10	0	1,91
Total	N=110		7,28/4	1,82

As seen in Table 2, the arithmetic mean of the answers given to the questions about water pollution was found to be 1.82. It can be said that the environmental sensitivity of the students regarding water pollution is high. According to the answers given by the students, the lowest arithmetic mean (1,68) is the mean of the answers given to the question "Do you buy cleaning products by paying attention to whether they contain harmful chemicals?". The number of students who answered sometimes to this question out of 110 students is 35. Considering the age of the students, it can be said that not all of them shop for cleaning and have not had this experience. It can also be said that students are less sensitive than others in terms of buying cleaning products by paying attention to whether they contain harmful chemicals or not, taking into account that they do not cause water pollution. It is seen that the sensitivity of the students regarding the other items and the entire water pollution sub-factor is high.

According to this finding, it can be concluded that while the environmental sensitivity of the students about water pollution is generally high, some students are less sensitive about purchasing cleaning agents by paying attention to their harmful chemical content and they may not have experienced the experience of shopping for cleaning depending on their age. The answers given to other water pollution sub-factors show that students are sensitive about this issue.

Table 3. Environmental Awareness of Students about Soil Pollution

Questions	Always	Sometimes	Never	\bar{x}
	f	f	f	
9. Do you take care to use both sides of the paper you write on?	98	12	0	1,89
10. Are you frugal in the use of paper napkins under all circumstances?	92	18	0	1,84
11. Do you plant saplings taking into account the appropriate conditions for their growth?	83	27	0	1,75
12. Do you make sure that the waste reaches the waste bin?	100	10	0	1,91
13. Do you dispose of wastes in appropriate recycling bins so that they can be recycled?	102	8	0	1,93
14. Do you classify the waste when you throw it away?	102	8	0	1,93
15. Do you warn people around you to be sensitive about soil pollution?	86	24	0	1,78
Total	N=110		13,03/7	1,86

As seen in Table 3, the arithmetic mean of the answers given to the questions related to soil pollution was found to be 1.86. This mean is the highest arithmetic mean among the sub-dimensions. It can be said that the environmental awareness of the students regarding soil pollution is high and even they are most sensitive to soil pollution. The highest arithmetic mean (1,93) related to soil pollution was the mean of the answers given to the questions "Do you throw the wastes into the appropriate recycling bins so that they can be recycled?" and "Do you classify the wastes while throwing them away?". 102 out of 110 students stated that they always dispose of waste in recycling bins suitable for recycling and that they classify waste when disposing of it. 100 out of 110 students stated that they always make sure that the waste reaches the waste bin. It can be said that the most important reason for this is that the students are in a school where zero waste policies are implemented and zero waste training is given. According to the table, it is seen that the environmental awareness of the students on soil pollution is quite high and even stands out as the area where they are most sensitive about soil pollution. It is observed that students show a high level of sensitivity especially in the issues of throwing waste into appropriate recycling bins and classifying garbage. This may be a result of the fact that students are in a school where zero waste policies are implemented and they receive zero waste training. This finding shows that zero waste policies and environmental education positively affect students' environmental awareness. It can be said that such trainings contribute to students to develop a more conscious and responsible attitude towards environmental issues.

According to the answers given by the students, the lowest arithmetic mean (1,75) is the mean of the answers given to the question "Do you plant saplings taking into account the appropriate conditions for their growth?". Even to this question, no

student out of 110 students answered "never" and the number of those who answered "sometimes" was 27. Even in the item with the lowest arithmetic mean of the questions related to soil pollution, 83 students stated that they always plant saplings. As can be understood from these data, it is understood that a significant majority of the students always plant saplings by taking into account the appropriate conditions for their growth. It is seen that the awareness of the students regarding the other items and the entire soil pollution sub-factor is high. According to the data, students' environmental sensitivity about planting saplings seems to be lower than the other questions about soil pollution. Especially the low responses to the question "Do you plant saplings by taking into account the appropriate conditions for their growth?" are noteworthy. The fact that no student answered "never" to this question and only some of them answered "sometimes" may indicate that students are relatively less sensitive about planting saplings. However, it is seen that the answers given to other questions about soil pollution are generally high and show that students are sensitive about soil pollution. In particular, the fact that the majority of the students stated that they always plant saplings in other items related to soil pollution shows that their level of awareness on this issue is high. Therefore, it can be said that students are generally conscious about soil pollution and environmental awareness, but it should be taken into consideration that there may be a need to create more awareness about planting saplings.

Table 4. Environmental Awareness of Students Regarding Ecological Balance

Questions	Always	Sometimes	Never	\bar{x}
	f	f	f	
16. If you were/are married, would you pay attention to population planning by considering the ecological balance?	88	22	0	1,80
17. Do you think it is appropriate for humanity to conduct all kinds of experiments on humans and animals?	110	0	0	2,00
18. Would you warn the people around you to be sensitive about the protection of ecological balance?	84	26	0	1,76
Total	N=110		5,56/3	1,85

As seen in Table 4, the arithmetic mean of the answers given to the questions about ecological balance was 1.85. It can be said that the environmental awareness of the students regarding ecological balance is high. It is seen that none of the students answered "Never" to the question "Do you approve of any kind of experimentation on humans and animals for humanity?". It can be thought that the teacher's statement "Pay attention to question 17" caused all students to express that they do not approve of any kind of experiment on humans and animals for humanity. Another reason for this may be that the school has bird and cat houses and bird and cat feeders made from waste materials. According to the data, it is seen that the students are sensitive to the issues of ecological balance and animal rights. In particular, the fact that they never answered the question "Do you approve of any kind of experimentation on humans and animals for humanity?" shows that the students have a clear attitude on this issue and respect animal rights. In addition, students were impressed by the presence of bird and cat houses and bird and cat feeders made from waste materials in the school. It can be said that such practices can create awareness in children about environmental sensitivity and animal rights.

Table 5. Students' Awareness of Participation in Environmental Studies

Questions	Always	Sometimes	Never	\bar{x}
	f	f	f	
19. Do you participate in scientific studies such as seminars, panels, conferences on the environment?	83	27	0	1,75
20. Do you participate in the activities of voluntary organizations working on the environment?	72	38	0	1,65
Total	N=110		3,4/2	1,70

As seen in Table 5, the arithmetic mean of the answers given to the questions about participation in environmental studies was found to be 1,70. It can be said that the students are sensitive about participation in environmental studies, but the sub-dimension with the lowest arithmetic mean is participation in environmental studies. It is seen that 83 of 110 students stated that they always participate in scientific studies such as seminars, panels and conferences on the environment, while 27 of them stated that they sometimes participate. Out of 110 students, 27 of them never, 83 of them sometimes participate in the activities of voluntary organizations working on the environment. It can be said that this number is high because it is a school where zero waste policies are implemented. Because frequent trainings and seminars on environment, nature and waste are organized at the school. According to the data, it is seen that students are sensitive about participating in environmental studies, but the lowest average in this regard is in the "participation in environmental studies" sub-dimension. In particular, the fact that students stated that they sometimes participate in scientific studies on the environment shows that they can be expected to participate more in such activities in a school where zero waste policies are implemented. This situation reveals the need to further strengthen the school's environmental education and awareness-raising activities. Considering the impact of zero waste policies on environmental studies, it can be said that these studies can play an important role in increasing students' participation in environmental studies.

The arithmetic mean of the students' answers to 20 questions about environmental awareness was found to be 1.80. It can be said that the environmental awareness of the students regarding air, water, soil and ecological balance is very high, and the reason for this is that they are in a school where zero waste policies are implemented, trainings and practices are given on environmental pollution and waste. It was determined that the arithmetic mean of the students' environmental awareness about air pollution was 1,81, the arithmetic mean of environmental awareness about water pollution was 1,82, the arithmetic mean of environmental awareness about soil pollution was 1,86, the arithmetic mean of environmental awareness about ecological balance was 1,85, and the arithmetic mean of environmental awareness about participation in environmental studies was 1,70. Although the arithmetic averages are close and high, it can be said that students are more sensitive to soil pollution and less sensitive to participation in environmental studies. In a school where zero waste policies are implemented, it should be considered normal that the environmental sensitivity is quite high, especially in soil pollution, which is directly related to zero waste policies such as delivering garbage to the garbage bin, classifying it while delivering it and throwing it into appropriate recycling bins. Based on the data, it is seen that students have a high awareness of environmental awareness. This high sensitivity should not be surprising, especially in a school where zero waste policies are implemented and environmental

education is frequently carried out. High awareness of air, water, soil and ecological balance may reflect that these students have a general awareness and responsibility towards environmental problems. However, the lower awareness of participation in environmental studies may indicate that students need more encouragement to actively participate in environmental projects or initiatives. In this regard, it is important for the school to develop a variety of strategies to encourage participation in environmental work and to involve students more. In general, zero waste policies and environmental education seem to be effective in increasing students' environmental awareness, and further strengthening of such practices can contribute to environmental sustainability.

Table 6. Students' Views on the Environmental Education They Received

Questions	Yes	Partially	No	\bar{x}
	f	f	f	
21. Do you believe that you have received sufficient training to raise awareness about air pollution?	90	19	1	1,81
22. Do you believe that you have received sufficient training to raise awareness about water pollution?	95	15	0	1,86
23. Do you believe that you have received sufficient education to raise awareness about soil pollution?	90	20	0	1,82
24. Do you believe that you have received sufficient education to raise awareness about ecological balance?	93	17	0	1,85
Total	N=110		7,34/4	1,83

As seen in Table 6, the arithmetic mean of the students' answers regarding the environmental education they received during their education life was found to be 1,83. It is seen that the students stated that they received adequate education on air, water, soil pollution and ecological balance. The reason why the students stated that they received adequate education may be that they received continuous education about environmental pollution, wastes and environmental sensitivity at school, participated in seminars and practices, and participated in nature trips. The fact that the students obtained a high average for the environmental education they received shows that the school is effective in education on environmental issues and that students are made aware of these issues. The fact that they stated that they received adequate education especially on air, water, soil pollution and ecological balance issues shows that the school's environmental education curriculum focuses on these issues and provides students with a solid foundation in these areas. The fact that the students stated that they were actively interested in environmental issues through activities such as receiving continuing education, attending seminars and participating in practices shows that the school attaches importance to such activities and that students learn about environmental issues through practical experiences. The opportunity to participate in nature trips also shows that students have the opportunity to observe nature and ecological balance in the field and that these experiences enrich their environmental education. The high average scores of the students regarding environmental education seem to be a result of the school's successful approach to environmental awareness and education. Continuation and diversification of such trainings can increase students' interest in environmental issues and contribute to raising individuals who are more sensitive to environmental problems.

In the research, qualitative data were analyzed and interpreted after the quantitative data were analyzed in accordance with the quantitative-qualitative sequential transformational design. In this part of the research, the data collected through interviews with teachers were interpreted using a qualitative approach with content analysis. In line with the aims of the research, findings and interpretations were made regarding successful zero waste and environmentally friendly practices, the effects of waste and environmental protection trainings on student behaviors, students' environmental sensitivity after zero waste policies were implemented, and suggestions regarding zero waste and environmentally friendly practices according to teachers' opinions.

The results of the interviews with teachers about successful zero waste and environmentally friendly practices are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Successful Zero Waste and Environmentally Friendly Practices According to Teachers' Opinions

Themes and Codes	N	Opinions
Successful applications	6	Participation of students and families in campaigns such as paper, battery and cap collection.
➤ Waste-related campaigns	4	Consolidation of information through seminars.
➤ Seminar studies	3	Planting activities in the school garden.
➤ Garden cultivation	3	Integration of students and parents with the environment through nature cleaning with trips.
➤ Excursions	2	Making compost as fertilizer together with students.
➤ Compost work	2	Creating awareness of nature with animal feeders and birdhouses made from waste.
➤ Reuse of waste materials		

In the interviews with the teachers, when asked the question "What are the zero waste and environmentally friendly practices that you find successful in your school?" in order to discover successful practices in the school where zero waste policies are implemented, six of the teachers stated the campaigns on waste as successful zero waste and environmentally friendly practices. 4 teachers mentioned that seminar activities reinforced the knowledge, three teachers mentioned planting and planting activities in the school garden, three teachers mentioned environmental cleaning trips, two teachers mentioned making compost as fertilizer, two teachers mentioned making animal feeders and birdhouses from waste materials. They stated that these activities were successful and environmentally friendly practices in the school implementing zero waste policy. The interviewed teachers gave answers similar to the following examples.

Teacher 2: There was a campaign to collect paper, batteries and caps. Planting was done in a part of our garden and compost work was carried out in the same area. Animal feeders and birdhouses made from waste were used to raise awareness of nature. Information was reinforced through seminars. Waste bins were placed on each floor. Students were involved in painting competitions. With practices such as vinegar and pickle making, the healing that everything from nature adds to us was discussed.

Teacher 4: Our school is a very active and successful school in zero waste and environmentally friendly practices. It has a garden designed to develop zero waste and environmental awareness. Planting and planting works are carried out in this garden. Composting as fertilizer is done together with students. There are more than one zero waste bins in each corridor of the school.

Various trainings on zero waste and the environment were and are given to students and parents. Trips are organized with parents and students.

Qualitative research findings reflect teachers' views on successful zero waste and environmentally friendly practices in the school where zero waste policies are implemented. Teachers stated that these practices increased the school's environmental awareness and helped students develop environmental awareness. The examples shared by teachers include various aspects of zero waste policies. In particular, campaigns on recycling and reusing waste materials were considered as part of environmentally friendly practices. In addition, interactive practices with nature such as planting and planting activities in the school garden and composting reinforced environmental awareness by increasing students' sensitivity to nature. In addition, involving students and parents in this process through seminars, trips and trainings helped to spread environmental awareness to a wider community. The findings show that zero waste policies have the potential to increase environmental awareness in educational institutions. In particular, active participation of teachers in these practices and training students on environmental issues can contribute to future generations to be more environmentally friendly. The adoption of such zero waste practices in more educational institutions can be an important step for the dissemination of environmental awareness and sustainability.

The results of the interviews with teachers about the effect of waste and environmental protection education on student behaviors are shown in Table 8.

Table 8. The Effect of Waste and Environmental Protection Trainings on Student Behaviours According to Teachers' Opinions

Themes and Codes	N	Opinions
The effect of trainings on student behavior	5	Students developed environmental awareness.
➤ Environmental awareness	3	The number of students feeding animals and planting saplings increased.
➤ Animal and seedling breeding	2	Parents and students took active roles in campaigns.
➤ Participation in campaigns	2	They started to separate their wastes as paper-plastic-glass and throw them into waste bins.
➤ Difference between waste and rubbish		

In the interviews with the teachers, five of the teachers stated that waste and environmental protection trainings have made a change in your students?" to the question "Have you observed that waste and environmental protection trainings have made a change in your students?" asked to explore the impact of waste and environmental protection trainings on student behaviors in the school where zero waste policies are implemented. Regarding the effect of waste and environmental protection trainings on student behaviors, three teachers emphasized that the number of students feeding animals and planting saplings increased, two teachers emphasized that parents also participated in the campaigns and students took an active role, two teachers emphasized that waste is not garbage, but they started to separate waste into paper-plastic-glass and throw them into waste bins. Examples of teacher statements about the effect of waste and environmental protection education on student behaviors are given below.

Teacher 1: Students developed environmental awareness. The number of students feeding animals and planting saplings increased. With the trips, students cleaned the nature and integrated directly with the environment. Parents and students worked together in every campaign.

Teacher 3: More progress was made with knowledgeable families. Many students participated in the campaigns.

Teacher 5: Reflections were observed not only in students but also in the family, as well as an increase in conscious consumption in the society and reflections on the utilization of waste as upcycling. Children developed the awareness that waste is not rubbish. They did not throw waste on the ground.

Qualitative research findings show that zero waste policies and environmental protection trainings have positive effects on student behaviors in the school where they are implemented. Teachers state that waste and environmental protection trainings improve students' environmental awareness, students actively participate and increase their environmental responsibilities. In particular, it is stated that interactive activities with nature such as feeding animals and planting saplings have become widespread among students and more students participate in such activities. The increased participation of parents in the campaigns shows that zero waste and environmental protection trainings are effective not only at school but also in the lifestyles of families. This emphasizes the functionality of education as a tool for teaching environmentally friendly behaviors to students' families. In addition, changes in waste management issues such as separate collection of wastes and directing them to recycling instead of throwing them away have led students to understand that wastes are not garbage and to behave more consciously in this regard. Such behaviors of students are important steps for a sustainable environment. In conclusion, these findings suggest that zero waste policies and environmental protection education are effective in increasing students' environmental awareness and that such curricula can positively influence the environmental behavior of both students and families. The adoption of such education programs in more schools can be an important step towards environmental awareness and sustainability.

The results of the interviews with teachers about how students' environmental awareness changed after the implementation of zero waste policies are shown in Table 9.

Table 9. The Effect of Zero Waste Practices on Students' Environmental Awareness According to Teachers' Opinions

Themes and Codes	N	Opinions
The effect of applications on environmental awareness	4	They learnt about water footprint.
➤ Water footprint information	3	Increased the behavior of throwing garbage in the garbage bin to avoid polluting the environment
➤ Garbage disposal		
➤ Consumption awareness	3	They learnt about substances that harm the environment.
➤ Harmful substances	2	Consumption consciousness increased.

In the interviews with the teachers, four of the teachers stated that students learnt the concept of water footprint in response to the question "How was the environmental

awareness of the students after the implementation of zero waste policies in your school?" asked to explore the impact of zero waste practices on students' environmental awareness. Regarding the effect of zero waste practices on students' environmental awareness, three teachers emphasized that students paid more attention to environmental pollution and did not throw their garbage into the environment, three teachers emphasized that they learned about substances harmful to the environment, and three teachers emphasized that students' consumption awareness increased. Examples of teacher statements about the effect of zero waste practices on students' environmental awareness are given below.

Teacher 1: They better distinguished whether the materials they used were garbage or recycling. The behavior of throwing garbage in the garbage to avoid polluting the environment increased. They learnt about water footprint.

Teacher 4: I observe that their sensitivity to throw waste into the right bins has improved. Our students were also informed about the water footprint. I think that students have reached an important point in their level of knowledge on this subject.

Teacher 6: They say that trees give us breath. They know that less trees will be cut down with recycling. They say that if they ride bicycles and do not get in the car, if they do not wear perfume, bad gases will not be released into the air.

Qualitative research findings show that zero waste policies and environmental education have positive effects on students' environmental awareness. According to teachers' views, it is clear that zero waste practices have introduced environmental issues to students more closely. In particular, it is stated that environmental concepts such as water footprint are taught to students. This means that students have become more aware of water consumption and conservation of resources. In addition, it is stated that students are more careful about environmental pollution and take care not to throw their rubbish into the environment. The findings show that students' environmental responsibilities have increased and they behave more respectful to the environment. Increased consumption awareness is also an important finding. It is stated that students started to better understand the environmental impacts of their consumption decisions and started to make more sustainable choices in this direction. In addition, increased awareness of recycling can contribute to the proper management of waste and more effective use of resources. In conclusion, these findings show that zero waste policies and environmental education are effective in increasing students' environmental awareness. Implementing such programs in more schools can help young generations to be more aware and responsible for environmental issues, thus contributing to a more sustainable future.

The results of the interviews with teachers about what else can be done regarding zero waste and environmentally friendly practices are shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Teachers' Suggestions on Zero Waste and Environmentally Friendly Practices

Themes and Codes	N	Opinions
Teacher suggestions	4	Trainings should be practical and long-term.
➤ Practice	3	The participation of parents should be increased.
➤ Parent involvement		
➤ Community participation	2	Social participation should be increased.
➤ Custom work	1	Special work should be done with struggling students.

In the interviews with the teachers, four of the teachers suggested that the trainings should be applied and longer in duration to the question "What else would you suggest to be done about zero waste and environmentally friendly practices in your school?" asked to discover the suggestions of the teachers about zero waste and environmentally friendly practices. Regarding the teachers' suggestions about zero waste and environmentally friendly practices, three teachers said that students pay more attention to environmental pollution and do not throw their garbage into the environment, three teachers said that the participation of parents should be increased, and two teachers said that social participation should be increased. One teacher stated that special studies should be carried out with students who have difficulty. All of the statements of the teachers interviewed about what else can be done regarding zero waste and environmentally friendly practices are given below.

Teacher 1: Practical trainings with students. Increasing seminars for parents.

Teacher 2: Practices that encourage parents and students to work actively in common work areas can be done.

Teacher 3: Special work should be done with students who have difficulty in practice.

Teacher 4: Acting with the awareness that zero waste and environmentally friendly practices should always be in every aspect of their lives, I think that such practices and activities should be carried out at every grade level.

Teacher 5: It should be ensured that the students involved in the activities are more active, the way should be paved for them to set an example for other students, practices should be emphasized in the work with stakeholders, current changes in the way of becoming conscious practitioners should be followed in the teams established and exemplified by practice, of course, zero waste and environmentally friendly studies should be spread throughout the year by acting within the framework of a plan.

Teacher 6: It would be good if the waste collected by us is collected by the municipalities with the same care. I think not enough care is taken.

The qualitative research findings, teachers' suggestions on zero waste and environmentally friendly practices provide important guidelines for developing an effective environmental curriculum and increasing sustainable environmental awareness. Teachers recommend the use of hands-on methods for environmental education. This suggestion can enable students to experience environmental issues and develop a deeper understanding. It is important for parents to help their children develop environmental awareness. Increasing parental involvement by organizing seminars and co-working spaces for parents can spread environmental awareness to the wider community. Some students may have difficulties with environmental education. Therefore, it was emphasized that special studies should be conducted to focus on individual student needs. As can be understood from the findings, it was emphasized that zero waste and environmentally friendly practices should be continuously implemented in all areas of students' lives. This can ensure that environmental awareness is active not only at school but also at every stage of daily life. Teachers at the school where zero waste policies are implemented stated that environmentally friendly practices should increase social participation and raise conscious practitioners. This suggestion can contribute to the adoption of environmental awareness in a wider community and sustainable changes. Teachers suggest that municipalities should pay more attention to waste management processes. This suggestion can be seen as important especially in the effective management of waste collection and recycling. In conclusion, these suggestions of teachers provide an

important roadmap for making environmental education and zero waste policies more effective. Implementation of these suggestions can increase students' environmental awareness and contribute to a more sustainable future.

Discussion

The findings obtained in order to determine the environmental awareness of students and the views of teachers in a primary school implementing zero waste policy were interpreted and some conclusions were reached. In this section, the results obtained were discussed in the light of the research in the literature.

In a primary school implementing a zero waste policy, it was determined that students were highly sensitive to the environment. Students are highly environmentally sensitive about air, water, soil and ecological balance. It was determined that environmental sensitivity was positively affected in a primary school where zero waste policies were implemented, trainings and practices on environmental pollution and waste were provided. The qualitative findings obtained in the study also support this result. It shows that zero waste policies and environmental education are effective in increasing students' environmental awareness and encouraging environmentally friendly behaviors. This finding contradicts the finding of Kamaşak (2019) that there was no significant difference between the knowledge, feelings and behavioral attitudes towards the environment of the students to whom the zero waste project was implemented in the 7th grade. This can be interpreted that the quality of zero waste-related trainings may differ according to schools and it becomes more difficult to gain sensitivity as the age level increases. Differences may arise not only from the school but also from the quality of environmental education in the region and country. For example, in a recent study conducted by Zwolińska et al. (2022) in Poland, it was emphasized that university students have environmental awareness. In a study conducted by Ulusal (2022) to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes and behaviors of adults about zero waste in Karatay district of Konya, Turkey, it was found that the knowledge, attitudes and behaviors of adults about zero waste were not sufficient. Zero waste policy is not only about separating waste and delivering it to the waste bin. The underlying principle of zero waste is to reduce environmental pollution and waste (Bagu & Arellano, 2021).

Students are mostly sensitized to soil pollution. Students in schools implementing zero waste policies develop sensitivity mostly on delivering garbage to the garbage bin, classifying it while delivering it and throwing it into appropriate recycling bins. It has been determined that zero waste policies develop students' awareness mostly about delivering waste to the waste bin and sorting it. In the study conducted by Young et al. (2010), zero waste policy is not limited to classifying and delivering waste to the bin. It is necessary to establish a waste recycling program, promote clean production, a green purchasing program and raise public awareness. It was emphasized that since the implementation of zero waste policy in Taiwan in 2003, the volume of waste for landfill and incineration has decreased significantly, recycling and minimization of domestic waste decreased by 37% in 2007 and industrial waste decreased by 76% by the end of 2006. When there is the necessary effort and motivation, it can be seen that zero waste policies and environmentally sensitive efforts yield results. In our study, it was determined that the students in the school where zero waste policies were implemented were less sensitive about participating in environmental studies compared to other environmental issues. In the study conducted by Çabuk and

Karacaoğlu (2003), it was determined that students were less sensitive about participating in the activities of voluntary organizations working on the environment compared to other environmental issues. Eales and Donaldson (2016), describing the success of a small private initiative in Australia, gave an example of a model that respects the environment and builds a new community by purchasing a suburban primary school to prevent its demolition. This model succeeded in reducing the use of mains-supplied drinking water and the discharge of used water through rainwater and sewerage systems. In Australia, where this success was achieved, approximately five billion dollars' worth of food is wasted every year (Lehmann, 2010). It is clear that there is a need to increase environmentally sensitive practices that can be a model for every country. Lee et al. (2020), in his research on China, which is the country with the highest population and perhaps the highest waste, mentions the support of zero waste cities. It is emphasized that waste can be used as a secondary carbon feedstock to replace fossil resources for production, contributing to environmental protection and resource conservation. Ridgefield High School, a local public school in Connecticut, USA, initially diverted all cafeteria waste to landfill, with recycling bins only in teachers' offices and certain classrooms. An initial waste audit of the cafeteria trash determined that of the 258 pounds of waste collected, the probability of diversion from the waste stream was 82.5%, including liquid, mixed recyclables, food, paper, 5-cent recyclables, and cardboard. Building the necessary infrastructure for recycling and composting alone will not solve their or any K-12 school waste management problem. This will be achieved through the history of environmental education in K-12 schools, environmental psychology, and improved environmental design of infrastructure to encourage recycling and composting in students, creating a cultural shift (Boyle, 2023).

Regarding air pollution, it was determined that the students always pay attention to the fact that other people are not affected while talking and using various vehicles. Despite the high level of environmental awareness about air pollution, the issue that the students showed less sensitivity than the others were the willingness to use public transport. The study conducted by Karacaoğlu and Karacaoğlu (2023) also shows that one of the issues that children, young people or adults in Turkey show the least awareness about air pollution is the use of public transport. Like the students in our study, it was found that a significant majority of their teachers did not always prefer public transport. It was determined that students, like their teachers, were relatively less sensitive about using public transport, taking into account not causing air pollution. The fact that the results are similar in different studies perhaps means that social impact should be increased and public transport facilities should be strengthened. Tzvetkova (2017) emphasizes that positive social impact can be achieved through the use of modern and environmentally friendly means of transport that reduce harmful emissions and noise impact on the health of the population. The primary goal of socially effective public transport is to ensure passenger travel by combining accessibility for all, comfort, awareness, efficient and stable urban intelligent transport systems and modern integrated environmentally friendly public transport with better emission indicators. In addition, ensuring safety and security while travelling will also contribute to the preference of public transport.

It has been determined that students are relatively less sensitive to water pollution in terms of purchasing cleaning agents by taking into account whether they do not cause water pollution and whether they contain harmful chemicals. According to teacher opinions, it was determined that students learnt the water footprint, i.e. water consumption, by the students at school. In a nationwide study conducted by Mei et al. (2016), it was determined that the highest environmental sensitivity of Malaysians was

on water pollution. However, it was emphasized that the result showed the opposite for climate change, and it was stated that this result was due to cost savings for water and energy. It was stated that the sensitivity about water pollution was due to cost saving rather than environmental sensitivity. According to Turan (2017), the protection of Turkey's water resources is extremely important for its economic sustainability and one of the important components of water management is water efficiency and one of the important sub-components of water efficiency is the rational use of water and water resources. The first approach to be implemented in this regard is to reduce water consumption per capita and in the society, both in production and consumption stages.

Regarding soil pollution, which was determined to be the most sensitive of the students, it was determined that they always threw the wastes into the appropriate recycling bins for reuse and classified the wastes while throwing the garbage. It was determined that the students in the school implementing zero waste policy always pay attention to the waste reaching the waste bin. The most important reason for this is that the students are studying in a school where zero waste policies are implemented and zero waste training is given. Even in the issue of planting trees related to soil pollution, where the lowest environmental awareness was determined, it was determined that most of the students always planted saplings taking into account the appropriate conditions. According to this result, it can be said that zero waste policies contribute positively to soil pollution the most. Bagu & Arellano (2021) emphasized that the implementation of zero waste policies will benefit the reduction of plastic pollution occurring both on land and in water, and suggested the implementation of zero waste depots at different points to gradually reduce the use of plastic and garbage in homes.

It was determined that the environmental awareness of the students regarding the ecological balance was high and that all students in the school did not approve of all kinds of experiments on humans and animals. It was concluded that bird and cat houses and bird and cat feeders made from waste materials at the school contributed to students' sensitivity to animals and nature. This practice can actually be considered as a small example of the "reduce-reuse-recycle-recover-store" waste hierarchy with extensive experience in circular carbon technologies (Lee, et al., 2020). As highlighted by Song et al. (2015), the concept of zero waste is proposed as a way to address environmental concerns, as the growing population, booming economy, rapid urbanization and rising community living standards have significantly accelerated the generation of solid waste in the world. Solid waste has now become one of the global environmental problems. As a result of the continuous depletion of natural limited resources, sustainable production, controlled consumption and strategic waste management are required to prevent further depletion of global resources as our world is heading towards an uncertain future.

It was determined that students were sensitive about participating in environmental studies. It was concluded that in a school where zero waste policies are implemented, frequent trainings and seminars on the environment, nature and waste are organized, which enables students to participate in environmental studies. In schools where zero waste policies are not implemented, students' environmental awareness may differ. For example, Negev et al. (2008) conducted a national survey to assess the environmental literacy of 6th and 12th grade students in Israel, including the dimensions of environmental knowledge, attitude and behavior. The study found no significant relationship between knowledge and behavior. Research findings show that the intended goals of environmental education in Israel have not been achieved. On the

other hand, a study conducted by Tuncer et al. (2005) in Ankara, the capital of Turkey, concluded that young people have widespread support for environmental protection. According to Bogusz et al. (2021), the amount of household waste in the European Union countries in 2019 was approximately 225 million tones. This means that each EU citizen produces an average of 502 kg of waste per year. This astonishing statistic necessitates environmental awareness and waste management.

It was determined that students received adequate education on air, water, soil pollution and ecological balance. Organizing curricula related to environmental pollution, wastes and environmental sensitivity at school, students' participation in environmental seminars and practices, nature trips positively affect students' environmental sensitivity. Activities related to waste can also contribute to environmental awareness. Because waste production is not a natural but a human activity. Although landfilling and incineration are common waste management techniques, the use of these techniques not only wastes raw materials but also damages the environment, water, soil and air. In the new "Zero Waste" concept, waste should be recognized as a valuable resource (Bogusz et al., 2021; Yazdani & Lakzian, 2023). Increasing air, water and soil pollution; deforestation and scarcity of resources and materials - overconsumption and unsustainable production processes are the causes of climate change, including biodiversity loss. Prevention of climate change and sustainability can be achieved through education policies that will make society more sensitive to the world we live in. Emerging complex global issues, such as health and the environment or lifestyles and consumption and development, require developing approaches and curricula that cross traditional boundaries between disciplines. Today, it is increasingly recognized that we need to discuss resource efficiency and resource recovery in the same way we currently discuss energy efficiency. This includes waste minimization strategies and the concept of designing waste out of processes and products. At local level, each municipality or company can act immediately to identify its own specific solutions. Some basic measures are to separate recyclable materials such as paper, metal, plastics and glass bottles and to combine all defined waste categories in a single collection point. To take basic measures, it is possible to build basic environmental sensitization and environmental protection skills in societies. However, a waste stream analysis should be carried out, including an inventory of the entire waste composition, measurement of the volumes of the different material categories and their origin and destination. Municipalities can set up databases to track all types of waste and cross-reference by type of facility, so that the amount and type of waste generated by each facility, district or region can be determined and thus where reduction is most appropriate. The concept of "zero waste" directly challenges the common assumption that waste is inevitable and has no value, by focusing on waste as a "misallocated resource" that should be recovered. It also focuses on preventing the generation of waste in the first place (Lehmann, 2010). All these efforts will be possible through education policies and curricula that will promote sustainability, climate change, environmental awareness and zero waste understanding. According to Bogusz et al. (2021), legal regulations and curricula should be seen as priority issues in the context of waste management. Likewise, Orlovic Lovren et al. (2020) emphasised that environmental awareness and sustainability can be achieved through education and curricula. In addition, organizing more training programs on environmental pollution and waste management in schools, encouraging students to participate in environmental seminars, increasing applied nature trips and supporting projects for environmental awareness will contribute to a sustainable environment. Acquisitions aiming to further increase the environmental awareness of students and to create a

sustainable environmental awareness can be increased in the curriculum related to different levels and courses.

The results show that in a primary school where zero waste policies are implemented, students' environmental awareness has increased and their awareness of important issues such as air, water, soil and ecological balance has increased. However, students need to develop more sensitization in some areas such as the use of public transport. Therefore, environmental curricula should not be limited to waste management, but should also include public transport and similar topics. Furthermore, in order to further increase environmental awareness, more emphasis should be placed on environmental education in schools and activities such as hands-on nature trips and environmental projects should be encouraged. In conclusion, it is concluded that zero waste policies can be an effective tool in educating students on environmental awareness and sustainability issues and it is important to integrate these policies more into educational curricula.

The qualitative findings of the study show that in a school environment where zero waste policies and environmental protection education are implemented, there are positive effects on student and teacher behavior. Valuable opinions of teachers reveal that such programs are effective in increasing environmental awareness and introduce environmental issues to students more closely. It has been observed that students' environmental awareness has improved and increased their environmental responsibilities. It was also noted that these curriculums spread to the wider community by influencing the lifestyles of families. The research findings emphasize that the adoption of environmental education and zero waste policies in more educational institutions can be an important step towards environmental awareness and sustainability. Recommendations support the development of an effective environmental curriculum and the dissemination of such practices to the wider community.

The quantitative and qualitative findings of the study show that zero waste policies and environmental education are effective in increasing students' environmental awareness and promoting environmentally friendly behaviors. Teachers' views clearly reflect that zero waste practices increase the school's environmental awareness and help students develop environmental awareness. These results show that students are motivated to recycle and reuse waste materials and behave more environmentally conscious as part of zero waste practices. It is also noted that environmental protection trainings increase students' environmental responsibility and draw more attention to environmental problems such as environmental pollution. The involvement of parents in this process has emerged as an important factor in developing children's environmental awareness. It is seen that by creating seminars and common working areas for parents, environmentally friendly behaviors of families are encouraged and these behaviors are transferred to children. Increased consumption awareness of students shows that zero waste policies and environmental education are effective in developing sustainable consumption habits. In addition, increased awareness of recycling has led to more conscious behaviors in waste management. The results of the research emphasize that zero waste policies and environmentally friendly practices should be adopted in more schools. In particular, the active participation of teachers in such practices and the wider dissemination of environmental education for students can increase the environmental awareness of future generations and contribute to a sustainable future. In conclusion, this research shows that zero waste policies and environmental education have the potential to increase students' environmental awareness and that

such programs provide opportunities for both students and families to improve their environmental behavior. The adoption of such programs in more schools could be an important step towards promoting environmental awareness and sustainability.

The results show that students are sensitive to air, water, soil and ecological balance and that zero waste policies positively affect this awareness. However, when compared with the results in different studies, it provides suggestive clues on how the quality of zero waste education and age level can affect sensitivity. In addition, differences were identified in issues such as students' level of participation in environmental studies and use of public transport. The research emphasizes the importance of combining zero waste policies with environmental education at school level and increasing environmental awareness. These results provide a notable contribution to the development of educational policies and curricula in terms of sustainability and environmental awareness. It was found that environmental awareness was positively affected in a primary school where zero waste policies were implemented, trainings and practices on environmental pollution and waste were provided, and students developed sensitivity to soil pollution the most. It was determined that zero waste policies developed students' sensitivity mostly about delivering waste to the waste bin and sorting it. It was determined that students were relatively less sensitive about using public transport, taking into account not causing air pollution. It has been determined that students are relatively less sensitive to water pollution, mostly taking into account not causing water pollution, and buying cleaning agents by paying attention to whether they contain harmful chemicals or not. It was determined that the environmental awareness of the students regarding ecological balance was high and that all students in the school did not approve of all kinds of experiments on humans and animals. It was concluded that bird and cat houses and bird and cat feeders made from waste materials at the school contribute to students' sensitivity to animals and nature. It was determined that students in a primary school implementing a zero waste policy were sensitive about participating in environmental studies. It was determined that students received adequate education on air, water, soil pollution and ecological balance. The organization of curricula on environmental pollution, waste and environmental sensitivity at school, students' participation in environmental seminars and practices, nature trips positively affect students' environmental awareness. Environmental education curricula should be implemented in more primary schools and more active participation of teachers and parents in the curricula should be encouraged. It is also important that zero waste policies are adopted more widely and that the public is made more aware of this issue. However, environmental sustainability issues such as energy saving and public transport should also be emphasized. Finally, it is of great importance that such efforts to raise environmental awareness are supported and disseminated not only within the school but also in the wider community. Implementation of these recommendations can increase students' environmental awareness and contribute to a more sustainable future.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings of this study indicate that the implementation of zero waste policies in a primary school environment significantly enhances students' environmental awareness, particularly with regards to air, water, soil, and ecological balance. While the study suggests that the quality of zero waste education and age levels may influence sensitivity variations, it underscores the importance of integrating zero waste policies with comprehensive environmental education programs at the school

level. Additionally, encouraging active participation of teachers and parents in environmental curricula, along with promoting sustainable consumption habits and increased awareness of recycling, can play a pivotal role in nurturing environmentally conscious behaviors among students. These results emphasize the potential for zero waste policies and environmental education to foster a heightened sense of environmental responsibility, contributing to a more sustainable future. Furthermore, the study recommends the wider adoption of such policies in educational institutions and an expanded focus on environmental sustainability issues such as energy conservation and public transportation, both within schools and throughout the broader community. Implementing these recommendations can lead to increased environmental awareness and contribute to a more sustainable future for our students and society as a whole.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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